

Management of Pancreatic Trauma at Tertiary Care Centre in North India: A Single Centre Experience

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Abstract

Background: The pancreas is an infrequently injured organ in abdominal trauma, often associated with other visceral injuries. Because of its retroperitoneal location, symptoms and signs of abdominal injuries are less evident/covert. The majority of pancreatic injuries are low-grade and are treated conservatively. A key factor in the treatment of pancreatic trauma is an injury to the main pancreatic duct. We conducted this analysis to discuss current management strategies available for pancreatic trauma.

Methods: A retrospective analysis of a prospectively maintained database of pancreatic trauma patients referred to the Department of Surgical Gastroenterology, King George Medical University, tertiary care teaching hospital from December 2020 to July 2023 was done. Demographic parameters along with mode, grade of injury, type of management have been recorded and analysed. Contrast-enhanced CT abdomen was done in all patients and the American Association for Surgery of Trauma (AAST) classification was used for grading of injury.

Results: Our study included 51 patients, of whom grade III injuries accounted for 78% of all injuries, followed by grade II injuries (10%). These patients received multimodality care for their injuries, while grade I and II injuries (7 patients) received conservative treatment.

Conclusion: Pancreatic trauma is uncommon and its management depends on the grade of injury. A multidisciplinary team including a medical gastroenterologist, interventional radiologist, intensivist and surgical gastroenterologist is necessary for optimal outcomes.

Introduction

Pancreatic injuries, albeit relatively uncommon, 0.2% in blunt trauma and 1-12% in penetrating trauma [1] present a significant challenge to clinicians because of their varied manifestations, which include infection, malnourishment, fistula formation, haemorrhage, multiorgan dysfunction, and mortality. Its retroperitoneal location and subtle symptoms in trauma leading to delayed/missed diagnosis are mainly responsible for its low prevalence. About 15% to 55% of patients have isolated pancreatic injuries in blunt trauma abdomen, but these are exceedingly rare in penetrating trauma [1,2]. Despite being a rarity, these are often associated with high rates of morbidity of 50% to 64% and mortality of 12% to 33% [3].

The treatment of pancreatic trauma has advanced significantly, and a paradigm change in improved clinical procedures and the establishment of tertiary

care trauma hospitals with a comprehensive range of resources has been developed [4-7]. In the present era, pancreatic trauma requires close coordination between a multi-disciplinary team which comprises an experienced pancreatic surgeon, endoscopist, intensivist and interventional radiologist [8].

Methods

This is a retrospective review of a prospectively maintained database comprising all patients admitted with trauma abdomen at the Department of Surgical Gastroenterology at tertiary care centre, India between December 2020 and July 2023. The study plan was approved by ethical committee. The hospital mainly caters to the low and middle socioeconomic strata of the Indian population and has round-the-clock emergency services, imaging, operating theatres and sub-specialty services available. Patients with a history of trauma and CECT abdomen & pelvis showing

More Information

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Keywords:

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evidence of pancreatic injury were included. We excluded pregnant and <14 years of age patients. The severity of the injury has been graded based on the American Association of Surgery for Trauma (AAST) scale (anatomical classification of pancreatic injuries) and the hemodynamic stability. Management was based on hemodynamic stability, the presence of ductal injury, associated organ injury, complications of pancreatic trauma and the availability of interventional procedures. Patients' management was divided and labelled as operative management (**OM**) – for those who underwent laparotomy or a minimally invasive procedure. The second group of patients were labelled as Non-Operative management (**NOM**) which included those that were managed conservatively or required serial aspirations and/or PCDs, endoscopic procedures and video assisted retroperitoneal debridement (VARD). The overall management of these patients along with the treatment for other associated injuries was recorded.

Various factors were considered to choose the best course of action, such as the mode of the trauma (penetrating vs. blunt), hemodynamic instability, injuries to related organs, delay in diagnosis or presentation, severity of the injury, and the feasibility of interventional techniques. Outcome measures for patients who underwent laparotomy or a form of minimally invasive procedure such as endoscopic drainage, cystogastrostomy, stent deployment or VARD included data related to recovery, mortality and morbidity including pseudocyst formation, pancreatic fluid leak, wound infection, and duration of hospital stay. Any complications related to the procedure were recorded in the proforma. Those patients who underwent image-guided (USG/CT) percutaneous catheter drainage (PCD) placement, morbidity in terms of catheter related complications, number of PCD and re-insertion of PCD were duly recorded. The minimum postoperative follow up period was three months or death. Figure 1 shows bar diagram of the grade of injury and their management.

Figure 1: Bar Diagram Showing Grade of Injury and Their Management

The data set was analysed for patients' demographic profile, mechanism of injury, severity, management and outcome. The data also included serially recorded parameters like pulse, systolic blood pressure (SBP), Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) and interventions done, if any. All continuous variables were represented as mean with their standard deviation and categorical variables

as counts and proportions. SPSS Statistics 22.0 software was used for analysis.

Results

A total of 51 patients were included in the study. About 80% of patients were males (n= 41) with age varying between 14 to 75 years with the median age being 36 years. The main mode of injury was road traffic accident

(RTA) accounting for 76% of the patients. All patients had a GCS score of 15 at the time of admission. Table 1 and Table 2 show the demographic profile of the patients and associated injuries respectively. All patients had elevated lipase and amylase levels in our study. However, there was no correlation between amylase level to grade of injury. The utility in clinical practice is hence limited to raising suspicion of pancreatic injury in patients with equivocal clinical findings.

All patients underwent axial imaging in the form of a CECT scan abdomen & pelvis which helped to grade and to rule out any major organ injury that would necessitate urgent treatment. Serial or repeat CT scans were done for selected patients as warranted by the clinical scenario. Additionally those patients with suspected aneurysms or haemorrhage underwent triple-phase CT angiography abdomen and pelvis. Grade III injuries were the most common being about (n=40, 78.4%) followed by grade II (n=5, 9.8%). MRCP was done in selected patients with Grade III injuries in those who were planned to undergo ERCP and pancreatic duct(PD) stenting as a part of the treatment algorithm to assess the status of main pancreatic duct(MPD) and the extent of disruption. These mainly included those patients who presented within a month from the date of injury.

Table 1: Demographic details

Parameter	
Age(Years)	
<20	12
21-40	23
41-60	8
>60	8
Sex	
Male	41
Female	10
Mechanism of injury	
Road Traffic Accidents	38(76%)
Assault	4(8%)
Falls	4(8%)
Penetrating Injury	1(2%)
Others	1(2%)
Length of stay (Days)	
Range	8-64
Median	16
AAST grade injury	
I	2(4%)
II	5(10%)
III	40(78%)
IV	3(6%)
V	1(2%)

Note: AAST: American association for surgery of trauma

Table 2: Associated injuries

Associated injuries	No. Of patients (%)	Management
Liver	11 (19.6)	10 Conservative 1 Perihepatic packing
Spleen	7 (13.7)	2 DPS 5 Splenectomy
Bowel	3 (5.8)	2 Resection anastomosis 1 Resection and stoma
Renal	2 (3.9)	1 Nephrectomy 1 Conservative
Bone	5 (9.8)	
Hemothorax	3 (5.8)	

Note: DPS: Distal pancreaticosplenectomy

Non-operative management

Low grade injuries (AAST I-II) were managed conservatively or with PCDs. Patients presenting with acute fluid collection (AFC) and pancreatic ascites were initially managed using endoscopic or image guided PCD placement. 5 patients were managed conservatively and 2 patients required PCD into the peripancreatic collection. For patients with Grade III injury with duct disruption and AFC in the lesser sac and/or pancreatic ascites endoscopic drainage along with single or double pigtail stent placement or percutaneous transgastric PCD was the initial treatment of choice. The transgastric stent was

internalized 4-6 weeks after the recovery of the patient. This was done with the view to avoid the formation of an external pancreatic fistula.

Selected patients with partial duct disruption and grade III or IV injuries with haemodynamic stability can be managed by ERCP and PD stenting. Insertion of nasopancreatic stents via the ampulla is also one of the recently described interventions for disrupted duct for control of pancreatic ascites. Also, patients with complete MPD disruption with delayed presentation beyond 7 days or presumed or infected collections were considered for PCD placement as the initial step.

In our series, out of 40 grade III injuries, 26 were managed via this NOM approach (Table 3). Patients managed with percutaneous PCDs required on median 2 sessions including upsizing of catheters. Also, VARD was done for 5 patients in whom the acute necrotic collection (ANC) could not be drained completely via PCDs or was considered too “thick” for drainage even with a 20Fr catheter. When placing

multiple PCDs, efforts were made to arrange them so that cross-irrigation might develop between the PCDs. Patients with “blush” or suspected pseudoaneurysm underwent digital subtraction angiography. In our series, 6 patients had bleed from pseudoaneurysm. 5 patients had a splenic artery pseudoaneurysm and underwent coil embolization and 1 from a common hepatic artery underwent covered stent placement.

Table 3: Management of grade III injury patients

Grade III injury(AAST)	Non operative management		Operative management	
	Transgastric PCD	6	Distal Pancreaticosplenectomy	2
Endoscopic drainage	7	Open Cystogastrostomy	9	
PCDs +/- VARD	11	Laparoscopic Cystogastrostomy	2	
PD stenting / nasopancreatic stenting	2	Open Roux en Y Cystojejunostomy	1	
Total	26		14	

Note: PCD: Percutaneous catheter drainage; VARD: Video assisted retroperitoneal debridement; PD: Pancreatic duct

Operative management

Patients presenting with a pseudocyst following a history of trauma were considered to have a ductal injury until proven otherwise. These patients underwent an internal drainage procedure either open, endoscopic or laparoscopic in the form of cystogastrostomy or roux-en-Y cystojejunostomy only if the pseudocysts were symptomatic. Even after multiple and repeated percutaneous interventions one patient developed pseudocyst 4 months after trauma and underwent laparoscopic cystogastrostomy.

Distal Pancreatectomy (DP) +/- Splenectomy was considered for patients presenting within 7 days of injury with grade III injury and complete MPD disruption. In our series, 2 patients underwent distal pancreatectomy with splenectomy while 12 underwent Internal drainage. The patients who underwent internal drainage were those who presented beyond 4 weeks of history of trauma with encapsulation. Laparotomy and lavage was only considered for patients wherein VARD or PCD placement was deemed not feasible/unsuccessful. One patient with grade IV injury underwent exploratory laparotomy and lavage with multiple drain placement and feeding jejunostomy. The patient was discharged with the drain in situ with a controlled pancreatic fistula.

Trauma Whipple is used as a last resort for patients with Grade IV- V injuries after other modes of treatment were exhausted or were deemed to have high failure rate by the team. Two patients in our centre underwent a Whipple procedure for duodenopancreatic head disruption. One patient was discharged with a pancreatic fistula (grade B) which resolved after 2 months. One patient developed grade C postoperative pancreatic fistula with subsequent

bleed from gastroduodenal artery pseudoaneurysm which required coiling. He, however, succumbed to sepsis on POD 22. Figure 2 shows the management of different grades of injury.

Discussion

Pancreatic trauma usually occurs secondary to high velocity trauma in the case of blunt trauma abdomen with the most common cause being road traffic accidents either due to direct compression or acceleration deceleration injuries. Our data was similar to other studies which showed RTA followed by assault as the most common mechanism of pancreatic injury [1-9].

Although amylase levels were found to be elevated in the majority of patients with pancreatic injury, still the specificity and sensitivity of serum amylase and lipase levels are low for the detection of pancreatic injuries. Also, there was no concordance between the degree of injury and hyperamylasemia. These findings were similar to studies conducted earlier [10,11]. Serum amylase can be elevated in 65-70% of patients with pancreatic injuries and 84% of patients had raised amylase after 3 hours [12]. Serum amylase and lipase can be elevated in patients without pancreatic injury also [14].

The evolution of pancreatic trauma usually follows a temporal cascade and a high degree of suspicion is required for the initial diagnosis. CECT is imaging modality of choice for all patients with suspicion of pancreatic trauma. CT abdomen has sensitivity of 33-100% and specificity is 62-100% for the detection of pancreatic injury. Adjuncts to diagnosis include MRCP to demonstrate extent of ductal disruption along with angiography in suspected cases of vascular injury.

Figure 2: Flow Diagram of Management of Various Grades of Injury

Apart from patients with complete pancreatic duct disruption and haemodynamic instability, the delay in referral or initial presentation is also an important factor in deciding between OM vs NOM. In our series, the results between the two groups were comparable, although a larger sample size is needed to prove any statistical significance. Also, the timing of presentation was different in both the groups in those who underwent upfront surgery and those managed with PCDs or endoscopic drainage.

Distal pancreatectomy with or without splenectomy is our preferred treatment for grade III injuries presenting acutely. It is our routine practice to close the duct using U sutures if the pancreatic duct is identified and buttress the stump using omentum. A single drain is placed near the pancreatic stump.

Our study describes various management options available for pancreatic trauma. Grade 3 and higher pancreatic injuries require multispeciality care and should preferably be referred to a tertiary medical centre.

It was a retrospective design and long term follow up was not included. As pancreatic injuries are less common, sample size was small. The effect of associated injuries on the final outcome could not be analyzed.

Prompt and apt intervention with a closely coordinated effort among experienced pancreatic surgeons, intensivists, interventional radiologists and endoscopists are the prerequisites for achieving optimal outcomes in patients with high-grade pancreatic trauma. An algorithmic approach to management plays a pivotal role in improving results.

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Statements and Declarations

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Conflict of Interest

None

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